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FOX: a Flexible and heterOgeneous miXed User Model to address Sustainable Behaviour in Smart Environments

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Abstract: Addressing how human behaviour can be taken into account when designing for sustainability is an emerging topic in the development of pro-environmental person-centred smart systems. Indeed, user diversity and categorisation in the context of sustainable behaviour has been already studied by some scholars in recent literature. However, the complexity of the individual present some open challenges that still have to be further investigated. In this work, behavioural theories and user characterisation are analysed together to better understand the human factors when trying to influence sustainable lifestyles and actions. Then, theoretical frameworks are combined and mapped in a novel user meta-model, coined FOX, that classifies the individual dynamically taking into account its heterogeneity and diversity. The dimensions involved in the FOX proposal are explained by describing the categorisation of each dimension. Besides, an example of the potential application of the model is exposed to better contextualise the work presented. Finally, controversial aspects and emerging ideas of the proposal are equally discussed throughout the paper as well as we discuss the use of FOX model to inform the design of behaviour change interventions related to sustainability.

Keywords: Sustainable Behaviour Change, Human Computer Interaction, User Modelling, Behavioural Theories, Smart Environments

1. Introduction

When developing technologies, in particular in the field of Smart Environments, the environmental impact should be taken into account. Sustainability has an uprising relevance that should be faced broadly. Sustainable Human-Computer Interaction (SHCI) aims at enhancing the environmental impact of technologies. Following the approach of Mankoff et al. [1] sustainability can be described through two main orientations: 1) sustainability *in* design, related to the optimisation of the materials and processes of the hardware and software; and 2) sustainability *through* design, related to influencing sustainable lifestyles and decisions. This way, SHCI addresses the relations and interactions of the individual with digital/tangible systems or technologies in order to improve sustainability [2]. Users' interactions and behaviours are therefore analysed to 1) better understand how to address the human factor; and 2) enhance the management of technological devices, systems

28 and processes in order to minimise its impact in the environment. Besides, this is a paramount
29 factor in human-centred intelligent environments [3], where actions are usually recognised to adapt
30 interventions and to offer feedback related to people's characteristics and needs. For that, it is necessary
31 to assume the complexity of the individual and to understand the different factors that may have an
32 influence on persons' behaviours and actions. [4] Thus, the study of the diversity of the individuals
33 emerges as a relevant issue. In this context, the fact that people are different from each other it must
34 be taken into account. Moreover, individuals also differ themselves depending on the moment, due
35 to many different factors (e.g. an individual with the habit of taking always the stairs instead of the
36 lift can change this due to a temporal injury). Therefore, heterogeneity needs to be understood as a
37 flexible and dynamic.

38 Following the ideas of Hekler et al. [5], to influence sustainable lifestyle and actions, behavioural
39 theories must be taken into account. Therefore, the paper is structured as follows: in Section 2
40 the state-of-the-art is analysed, exposing the theoretical frameworks to understand the behavioural
41 processes and other approaches that address the user diversity for sustainable behaviour. Next, the
42 FOX meta-model is described, detailing the dimensions and analysing the key factors that involve the
43 proposal. Section 4 offers a discussion of the most controversial issues, explaining the limitations of
44 the work. Then, the application of the model is exposed to contextualise the presented model. Finally,
45 in Section 5 the conclusions extracted from the research work are summarised and the future research
46 lines defined.

47 To avoid misunderstandings on terms used in this work, it should be clarified that the different
48 elements involved in the behavioural theories and frameworks are called *Constructs*. The elements that
49 compound the user meta-model are called *Dimensions*, being these based on the behavioural constructs
50 in most of the cases. Besides, these dimensions are understood in the context of the Behavioural
51 Technologies (BT) addressed to enhance the awareness towards sustainable behaviour.

52 **2. Behavioural theories and user models to improve the sustainable behaviour**

53 In this section, the state-of-the-art is described to analyse the most relevant works related to the
54 research presented in this paper. In order, to frame the theoretical context, first, we expose behaviour
55 change models applied to sustainability. Then, other complementary user models and characterisations
56 are described, and finally, conclusions of the revision of related work are resumed to contextualise the
57 contribution presented in this work.

58 *2.1. Theoretical frameworks of sustainable behaviour change*

59 In the literature, we can find different approaches to cope with the decision making process. In
60 this work, we highlight three relevant behavioural models that offer different approaches to frame the
61 actions of individuals.

62 **2.1.1. Transtheoretical Model**

63 The Transtheoretical Model (TTM) [6] is a longitudinal model that analyses the process of change
64 to understand how it happens. It divides the stages of behaviour change in six: pre-contemplation,
65 contemplation, preparation, action, maintenance and termination. There are other complementary
66 constructs as Process of change, Decisional Balance and Self-Efficacy. The Processes of change involve
67 ideas that are used to progress through stages. Decisional Balance is related to the advantages and
68 disadvantages of changing, and Self-Efficacy to the confidence in developing the desired behaviour
69 and the temptation to avoid it. This behaviour model has been applied to boost sustainable actions and
70 lifestyle by some scholars: He et al. [7] developed specific strategies to boost the pro-environmental
71 behaviour in the different stages of change. Besides, Wising, Chirez and Adams [8] proposed a work
72 using TTM to enhance industrial energy efficiency targeting the change of the energy culture. Figure 1
73 shows the different stages of the TTM.

Figure 1. The Transtheoretical model of behaviour change.

74 2.1.2. Values-Beliefs-Norms

75 The Theory of Values-Beliefs-Norms (VBN) is a theoretical framework for sustainable behaviour
 76 based on values and norm-activation processes (see Figure 2). The main idea of VBN is that individuals
 77 who accept a movement's basic values, believe that valued objects are threatened. Due to this, they
 78 trust that their actions can help restore those values and experience an obligation (personal norm)
 79 for pro-movement action that creates a predisposition to contribute giving support in different levels [9].
 80 This predisposition is linked to different types of implication levels, and in consequence, behaviour
 81 types. The different constructs proposed by this framework are chained. Thus, the values will affect
 82 the developed pro-environmental beliefs, creating a personal and subjective norm that will inform the
 83 sustainable behaviour change. The Subjective Norm is triggered when individuals perceive that certain
 84 behaviours they perform have negative impacts on questions on which they are confident. The values
 85 are intrinsic from the individual, but they may be aligned with the environmentalism and develop
 86 increasing beliefs that end up in the development of Pro-environmental Personal Norm. Beliefs appear
 87 with the New Ecological Paradigm, which is related to the acceptance of the fact that human actions
 88 harm the environment. The next step is to be aware of the consequences, and then the ascription of
 89 responsibility. Next, the norm will be created and the individual will adopt the behaviours and action
 90 according to this norm. This approach was refined later by Stern et al. [10]. Besides, Petkov et al.
 91 developed a study addressing interventions through feedback to different user types depending on
 92 the different values outlined by Stern's theory [11].

Figure 2. The Value-Belief-Norm theory of behaviour change.

93 2.1.3. Theory of Planned Behaviour

94 The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) [12], is a conceptual theory that addresses the intentions
 95 as the immediate antecedent of behaviour (see Figure 3). These intentions are influenced by
 96 Beliefs, Attitudes and Behavioural Control (the perceived Self-Efficacy over a specific action). This
 97 framework helps to understand how people's behaviour can be changed or directed with a series
 98 of predictable aspects that can influence the intended conduct. This theory is determined by the
 99 link of the decision-making process and the execution of the activity, being the intentional behaviour
 100 conditioned by three constructs: the subjective norm, the perceived ability or efficacy to perform the
 101 desired behaviour and the attitudes towards the behaviour. This framework has been applied to the
 102 pro-environmental context by Coskun and Erburg to face the user diversity for sustainable behaviour
 103 [4]. Besides, Greaves, Zibarras and Stride analysed intentions in relation to sustainability using TPB
 104 theory in the context of the workplace [13].

Figure 3. The Theory of Planned Behaviour.

105 2.2. User models and characterisations addressed to sustainability

106 In addition to behaviour change models, some works explore user diversity to understand how the
 107 individual behave. In this way, Lockton et al. developed user-profiles for sustainable behaviour taking
 108 into account the differences in behavioural traits, defining the Pinball, Shortcut and Thoughtful user
 109 types, based on the different models of the human system [14]. Coskun and Erburg proposed another
 110 categorisation, based on the TPB [15] and identified four personas in the context of the sustainability [4].
 111 Petkov et al., applied the VBN to develop a user categorisation to implement personalised eco-feedback
 112 [11] and He et al. [7] used the TTM to the same purpose. Cor and Zwolinski identified two types of
 113 individuals using questionnaires to measure the key-factors [16]. Lilley Bailey and Charnley developed
 114 personas focusing on the self-repair behaviour among other factors [17], Halko and Kientz addressed
 115 the differences on individuals' personality concerning behaviour change techniques [18], and Kaptein,
 116 Lacroix and Saini developed profiles based on the persuasion level [19].

117 2.3. Insights extracted from the literature analysis

118 After the review of related work, some conclusions can be highlighted to guide research on how
 119 to better understand the human factor to influence sustainable lifestyles and actions. Following the
 120 statement of Coskun and Erburg [15], there is no standard method to explore user heterogeneity and it
 121 is complicated to extract validated knowledge. Besides, each author applies a different approach with
 122 specific criteria in a specific context. Thus, it can be difficult to extrapolate knowledge and to further
 123 analyse the impact of these proposals. Moreover, most of the proposals are based on a single dimension
 124 of the user. Therefore, the application of existing taxonomies may lead to several shortcomings derived
 125 from the narrow view when not understanding the different factors that influence the individual [5].
 126 Finally, the lack of dynamic categorisation of the users among all the paper revised presents major a
 127 gap that should be tackled to improve the better understanding of the individual in every context.

128 3. Addressing the heterogeneity dynamically: the meta-model

129 Aiming at coping with the shortcomings revealed when analysing the state-of-the-art, this work
 130 proposes a meta-model of user characterisation addressing the heterogeneity and diversity of the
 131 individuals. This work combines behavioural approaches for sustainability in order to 1) face the
 132 shortcomings derived from the use of a single behavioural approach; 2) offer a unified theoretical
 133 background to address the design of specific and personalised behavioural interventions and 3) advise
 134 the limitations derived from the different contexts and environments that may influence specific
 135 behavioural dimensions. The framework presented in this work contemplates specific user dimensions
 136 that will help at boosting the awareness about sustainable actions. Hereafter we describe the specific
 137 behavioural dimensions and its implications. Figure 4 shows the elements and relations proposed in
 138 the envisaged model.

Figure 4. The FOX model with the specific dimensions and relations.

139 3.1. Stages of change

140 As previously exposed, the TTM approaches the behavioural process taking into account the
 141 stages of change in the time [6]. Although this model involves complementary constructs, *Stages of*
 142 *Change* set the basis of the framework, offering a key dimension to locate the user in a longitudinal
 143 position of the behaviour change process. The *Stages of Change* are included in the model as a
 144 whole dimension of the user, and phases are understood as the elements of this dimension. In
 145 the FOX model, the complementary constructs that involve the TTM (Process of Change, Decisional
 146 Balance and Self-Efficacy) are supplied through complementary dimensions (*Attitudes*, *Subjective Norm*,
 147 *Behavioural Control*, *Personality Traits*, *Values* and *Beliefs*) which act as reinforcement in the different
 148 phases. Following the pro-environmental approach proposed by He et al. [7], the stages of change are
 149 classified as:

- 150 • *Pre-contemplation*: The user has no intention to take action in the next six months.
- 151 • *Contemplation*: The individual intends to take action in the next six months.
- 152 • *Preparation*: The individual intends to take action within the next month and has taken
- 153 behavioural steps to face it.

- 154 • *Action*: Significant changes in behaviour within the past six months.
- 155 • *Maintenance and Relapse*: Besides significant changes in the behaviour for more than six months,
- 156 the person tries to sustain the acquired actions and to prevent the relapse.

157 3.2. *Personality*

158 When developing behavioural technologies, the diversity between individuals with similar
 159 context, values and habits (e.g. siblings, friends...) implies a differential factor. The diverse personalities
 160 can be determinant on the acceptance and adoption of the inputs. Therefore, this appears as a
 161 dimension that should be included when addressing user diversity for sustainable behaviour change. In
 162 this context, the characterisation proposed by Lockton et al. [14] [20] fits well due to the understanding
 163 of behaviour by approaching personality concerning pro-environmental behaviour. This author
 164 identified three user types: Shortcut (self-regulating models of the human system), Pinball (linear
 165 models of the human system), and Thoughtful (learning models of the human system).

- 166 • *Shortcut*: Self-regulating human models systems are understood as narrowly rational users, and
 167 makes choices to minimise energy or cognitive expenditure. This means wanting the fastest or
 168 easiest way to do things.
- 169 • *Pinball*: Linear human systems implies a user who only reacts simply to inputs, doing the same
 170 thing each time the same stimulus is applied and does not think about any decisions.
- 171 • *Thoughtful*: The learning human systems can be understood as people who think about what
 172 they are doing and why, analytically, being able to set and modify their own goals. In this
 173 classification, individuals learn from their mistakes and change their behaviour accordingly.

174 This classification is included in the FOX model as a *Personality* dimension to face different
 175 typologies regarding sustainable behaviour change. The elements of the dimensions are selective in
 176 each case due to the relation with the behavioural action, i.e. the individual may react differently to a
 177 particular input but must react in a single and specific way. For example: when receiving a mobile
 178 notification, the user may act ignoring it (self-regulating models), closing it (linear models) or opening
 179 it and reading the whole information (learning models). Thus, a single individual may act differently
 180 to an input, but the action will be only one in each moment.

181 3.3. *Attitudes*

182 Following the ideas of the TPB, behavioural beliefs produce a favourable or unfavourable
 183 attitude toward behaviour. Thus, sustainable attitudes can be related to the intrinsic and/or extrinsic
 184 motivations of individuals due to their different values. The attitudes can change dynamically
 185 depending on the situation and the behavioural values [21]. Encouraging the users and improving the
 186 attitudes towards sustainability, targets the motivational side, thus enhancing the awareness of the
 187 individual. For all of these reasons, this dimension is included in this work. Attitudes are categorised
 188 incrementally as follows:

- 189 • *No Environmental Attitude*: In this case, the user does not think about pro-environmental
 190 behaviour and therefore beliefs towards sustainable behaviour do not exist. The individual
 191 does not see its benefits or its immediate positive impact including other barriers that difficult
 192 positive beliefs toward sustainable behaviour.
- 193 • *Low Environmental Attitude*: The users' beliefs towards sustainable behaviour are not positive.
 194 The individual thinks that pro-environmental attitude may be positive, but does not see its
 195 benefits or its immediate positive impact. Besides, it may perceive several barriers that difficult
 196 positive beliefs toward the behaviour change.
- 197 • *Medium Environmental Attitude*: The users' beliefs towards sustainable behaviour are at the
 198 medium level. The individual thinks pro-environmental attitude is positive but perceives several
 199 barriers that difficult the fully positive beliefs toward the behaviour change.
- 200 • *High Environmental Attitude*: The users' beliefs towards sustainable behaviour are at the maximum
 201 level, thinking that pro-environmental attitude is very positive.

202 3.4. Behavioural Control

203 Behavioural control is another construct proposed by the TPB that is linked with control beliefs
204 of the user towards the specific target behaviour [21]. The Behavioural Control is related to the
205 perceived Self-Efficacy and is directly linked with the target action or behaviour change. It emerges as
206 a dimension that influences directly the pro-environmental behaviour of the individuals. Therefore,
207 *Behavioural Control* is included in the meta-model, being a key issue to analyse when addressing the
208 user diversity for behaviour change. The classification proposed is:

- 209 • *No Behavioural Control*: The user perceives that has no control over a specific behaviour.
- 210 • *Low Behavioural Control*: The user thinks that the desired behaviour is difficult and that there are
211 many barriers to face the desired action or behaviour.
- 212 • *Medium Behavioural Control*: The user thinks that is not difficult nor easy the target behaviour,
213 and that some barriers difficult the change.
- 214 • *High Behavioural Control*: The user perceives that the target behaviour is easy and affordable.

215 3.5. Subjective Norm

216 The subjective norm is based on how sustainable behaviour is perceived by the individual and
217 its context. Following Ajzen's idea, normative beliefs result in perceived social pressure or *Subjective*
218 *Norm* [21]. Therefore, if the importance of sustainability is a familiar concern to the individual and
219 his/her environment, the subjective norm may be high due to its relevance in the near context. This
220 idea was addressed also by Stern, et al., defining subjective norm as the sense of obligation derived
221 from the pro-environmental beliefs [9]. In this context, Ajzen's subjective norm is related to external
222 motivations and Stern's approach to more internal ones. In this work, the norm involves both intrinsic
223 and extrinsic motivations of the individual when developing a subjective norm: the pressure that
224 the environment may put in the person and the sense of obligation that the individual feels due to
225 his/her own beliefs. Taking into account that Subjective Norm is related to the internal rules of the
226 individual and it is included in the model to cover the personal norms of the individuals. In this way,
227 the *Subjective Norm* dimension is categorised as:

- 228 • *No Subjective Norm*: The individual does not have subjective rules about pro-environmental
229 behaviour and has neither internal or external pressure to adopt it.
- 230 • *Low Subjective Norm*: The individual feels that pro-environmental behaviour is not a bad idea but
231 does not feel important in his/her own life due to the absence of personal or social norm.
- 232 • *Medium Subjective Norm*: The individual feels that pro-environmental behaviour is a positive idea
233 but is not fully convinced and feels relaxed about the need to adopt the behaviour.
- 234 • *High Subjective Norm*: The individual feels that pro-environmental behaviour is an obligation due
235 to social and personal rules.

236 3.6. Values

237 Values is a dimension extracted from the VBN theory and involve the user personal concerns
238 related to sustainability. In this context, these are the starting point to acquire responsibility for
239 pro-environmental behaviour. Nevertheless, according to Petkov et al. values alone are not enough to
240 boost behaviour change [11]. Taking into account that individuals have different kinds of personal
241 values, motivation may be increased by improving these. Stern's paradigm proposes four types of
242 values related to the pro-environmental behaviour: Altruistic, egoistic, traditional and openness to
243 change [10]:

- 244 • *Altruistic*: These values are focused on avoiding threats for other people. Thus, altruistic
245 individuals are those care about others and for equality.
- 246 • *Egoistic*: These values are related to the needs and wants of the individual e.g. the gains and
247 loses.

- 248 • *Traditional*: Values related to security and to maintain the current status to preserve the habits
249 and traditions.
- 250 • *Openness to change*: Values related to the curiosity, involving individuals interested in different
251 problematic as sustainability. These values involve the stimulation derived from achievement
252 and improvement.

253 3.7. Beliefs

254 *Beliefs* are the last dimension extracted from the VBN and involve the concerns related to the
255 effects of human activity on the environment [10]. These are derived from values, following the idea
256 that things relevant to those values are under threat. This behavioural construct is included as a
257 dimension to better understand individual's beliefs concerning pro-environmental values. These are
258 related to the risk perceived on environmental problems, and they can be classified as:

- 259 • *Conscious*: This category involves the beliefs of the individual's that are accepting a new ecological
260 paradigm.
- 261 • *Aware*: This category are classifies individuals who are aware of the adverse consequence for
262 valued objects due to the environmental problem.
- 263 • *Responsible*: This category involves individuals that perceive the ability to reduce the threat and,
264 therefore, are more willing to take action and to adopt sustainable behaviour.

265 3.8. Mapping the dimensions: the meta-model

266 The analysed dimensions are mapped in a novel user-model that combines behavioural
267 approaches found in literature. Mixing and linking the most common theoretical models and
268 user-classifications may help avoiding a narrow perspective of each individual model by offering a
269 more complex way to understand the behaviour of individuals.

270 The classification proposed in this work includes different categories depending on the dimension.
271 There are quantitative categorisations e.g. *Attitudes*: indifference can be 0 value and the a positive
272 attitude 10. On the other hand, qualitative dimensions such as *Personality* or *Values* are divided by
273 qualities and specifications but cannot be understood in an incremental measurement context. This
274 way, categories such as *Beliefs* dimension may involve both approaches: consciousness, awareness,
275 and responsibilities are qualitative but also quantitative if they are understood as chained, being the
276 consciousness the first state and the responsibility the last.

277 The dimension *Stages of Change* has a longitudinal approach and it should be contextualised
278 through phases, where the individual is placed in any specific stage. Due to this, the FOX model
279 include all other dimensions along with the different phases, covering user diversity through all
280 the stages of the change process. This approach can be observed in Figure 4. *Personality* is another
281 dimension that is placed according to its specific nature. Taking into account that the "models of the
282 human system" proposed by Lockton et al.[14] involve a broad contextualisation of the individual in
283 regard to sustainable behaviour, this dimension is placed in the bottom of the model and linked with
284 the other elements of the model.

285 The other dimensions of the meta-model are linked following the relations proposed by each
286 behavioural model: 1) the dimensions extracted from constructs of the VBN are chained, being the
287 *Values* the starting point, the *Beliefs* based on the values the next item and *Subjective Norm* that user
288 develops based on two previous factors the last dimension. 3) *Attitudes*, *Behavioural Control* and
289 *Subjective Norm* are part of the TPB and therefore, these are linked to map the influence that each
290 dimension have in others. Hence, the dimensions preserve their placement and context proposed in
291 their own behavioural framework and should be understood with their links and relations to do not
292 miss the influences that each dimension can imply in others. *Subjective Norm* is included in the VBN
293 and TPB, and therefore, is placed as a single dimension related to both models and maintaining the
294 links (see Figure 4).

295 As we exposed previously, different behavioural models complement each other addressing
296 the complexity of the individuals. To better connect the different items, Figure 4 illustrate the links
297 through arrows. Following with this idea, each dimension acts complimenting others and reinforcing
298 the different approaches proposed by the theoretical frameworks.

299 4. Application of the meta model

300 One of the applications of this model is to be used to inform the design of behaviour change
301 interventions. This way, why and how these interventions improve awareness of sustainable behaviour
302 could be studied and analysed. To better understand the model and how it can be applied in design
303 and implementation of user heterogeneity when influencing sustainable actions, hereafter we expose a
304 simple textual example of a possible application using a *persona* [22]. This is in line with the approach
305 followed by He et al.[7] when describing the application of TTM to pro-environmental behaviour
306 change.

307 4.1. The example of Jon

308 Jon lives with Peter and their dog Zero in Berlin. He is 34 years old and recently started a new
309 job in a very prestigious architecture studio. He is hard-working and values productivity. He is very
310 familiar with computers and wears a health tracker among other smart devices.

311 4.1.1. The specific context of Jon

312 At Jon's new job, they are very concerned about the environmental impact of their buildings.
313 They try to reduce the energy demand of the buildings they design, and besides, they try to face the
314 sustainability of their workplace. Due to this, they have installed sensors across the building to capture
315 data and optimise the usage of processes and devices. Besides, they created a smartphone app named
316 Foxi to offer feedback and data about environmental concerns to motivate and influence workers.

317 4.1.2. Categorising Jon

318 In his second day at work, at lunchtime, Jon decides to download and use the app that his
319 company developed to boost the awareness about the importance of sustainable behaviour. To create
320 his profile, he answers some questions in the app. Next, he goes to his desktop and works normally. In
321 the following days, the Smart Environment of the workplace catches relevant data about Jon, and by
322 comparing it with the data of the app, a preliminary categorisation is implemented:

- 323 • *Stage of change*: Jon is categorised as *contemplator* because he recognises some problematic
324 behaviours and he is thinking of improving them.
- 325 • *Values*: His values are categorised as *altruistic*.
- 326 • *Beliefs*: Jon has been included in the *aware* category taking into account his environmental beliefs.
- 327 • *Subjective Norm*: The Subjective Norm of Jon is *medium*: in his work environment the norm is
328 very high but in other environments (at his home, for example) there are no a pro-environmental
329 norm.
- 330 • *Attitudes*: The attitudes of Jon regarding sustainable behaviour are categorised as *medium*.
- 331 • *Behavioural control*: The behavioural control of Jon in the context of his workplace is *low*.
- 332 • *Personality*: The personality of Jon is categorised as *Shortcut*.

333 4.1.3. Implementing interventions

334 Once Jon is located in the dimensions of the FOX model, specific interventions are implemented to
335 improve the awareness of pro-environmental lifestyle. Taking into account the existing categorisation
336 of Jon, the following strategies are implemented:

- 337 • *Stage of change*: In order to motivate Jon to change to next stage, preparation, the application
338 gives information of benefits of being sustainable.

- 339 • *Values*: The Foxi app offers a data visualisation of the impact of the climate change in other people
340 in different parts of the world to enhance the importance of being sustainable addressing values.
341 Besides, Jon can access to other relevant data taking into account other factors (e.g. economic
342 data, about the impact on animals and plants and so on).
- 343 • *Beliefs*: Taking into account the data gathered by sensors in Jon's workplace, they decide to
344 implement an awareness campaign showing data of the average energy waste of a single
345 individual at work and tips to avoid it, aiming at motivating workers at being responsible
346 with their own actions.
- 347 • *Subjective Norm*: To boost the Subjective Norm in relation to the sustainability, Foxi app shows the
348 profile and data of prominent pro-environmental people (in this case famous architects). Besides,
349 it offers a social network to boost relationships with other people with similar interests.
- 350 • *Attitudes*: To enhance pro-environmental attitudes, Jon's company showcased a documentary
351 film about the impact of climate change.
- 352 • *Behavioural control*: The Foxi app offers reminders that can be personalised by Jon. This way, he
353 does not forget turning off the devices when leaving the office.
- 354 • *Personality*: As a Shortcut user, he makes the effortless choice. Therefore, the Foxi app has every
355 single process set by default (favouring the most pro-environmental options).

356 4.1.4. Measuring and updating the model

357 Once the interventions are implemented, the next step is to compare whether there have been
358 improvements in motivation about sustainable behaviour. Through a short survey (by using the Foxi
359 app) and the data gathered by the Smart Environment, the new status is recognised and the model
360 updated.

- 361 • *Stage of change*: After the interventions, Jon started to plan new pro-environmental actions.
362 Therefore, the model updated this dimension and now Jon is in *preparation* stage.
- 363 • *Values*: The values of Jon were aligned with pro-environmental issues and now the altruism of
364 Jon involved sustainability concerns. Besides, he consulted data related to expenses and money
365 savings. Therefore, Foxi app improved the visibility of this data and the categorisation of Jon
366 changes from *altruistic* to *egoistic* dimension depending on the most viewed data.
- 367 • *Beliefs*: Jon has taken responsibility for the environmental problem. Therefore, its categorisation
368 changes to *responsible*.
- 369 • *Subjective Norm*: After the interventions, the Subjective Norm of Jon raised, and now is categorised
370 as *high*.
- 371 • *Attitudes*: In the update of the model, the attitude of Jon about sustainability raised and now Jon
372 has a high pro-environmental attitude.
- 373 • *Behavioural control*: After the interventions, the behavioural control of Jon is categorised as
374 *medium*.
- 375 • *Personality*: Jon maintains most of the time the Shortcut behaviour, but the system detected that,
376 mostly at the weekends, he checked other data (as his historic energy expense). Therefore, in
377 those days the app will give feedback to boost his knowledge and to help him to learn about his
378 behaviour.

379 5. Discussion

380 This early proposal combines behavioural models and categorisations to face the awareness
381 of sustainable actions and lifestyles. The main objective of this framework is to offer a theoretical
382 background that can be applied in several ways: to understand diversity (e.g. developing user
383 archetypes), to apply interventions to boost the sustainable behaviour and to analyse the relations and
384 causes of the different dimensions among others. Nevertheless, this proposal should be understood as
385 an incipient approach that needs to be further studied and analysed to address each specific context
386 and target users. Besides, other factors as demographics should be taken into account when applying
387 the model to understand the behaviour change process of individuals.

388 This proposal has been addressed based on theoretical frameworks applied to improve the
389 awareness and motivation about sustainable behaviour. Therefore, this model should be understood as
390 context-specific and should be contextualised to frame the pro-environmental behaviour. Nevertheless,
391 after the context-related literature review, the dimensions of this model may have the potential to be
392 adapted to other contexts.

393 The use of the model, in a broad sense, is a key point that should be discussed: on the one hand,
394 the analysis of specific dimensions can bring valuable knowledge that is needed to extract findings
395 on how to measure and categorise the users. Nevertheless, addressing a single specific dimension
396 without understanding the context offered by other dimensions and its relations may bring a narrow
397 view and involving several shortcomings [5]. Therefore, although addressing one specific dimension,
398 the context of the framework and the other elements and relations should be carefully understood and
399 analysed.

400 Considering this meta-model presents a novel categorisation, there are some limitations that
401 should be taken into account: 1) this model has not been tested yet, nor applied in experimental
402 conditions. Thus, can not be understood as a validated proposal; 2) the included dimensions target
403 attributes related to the behavioural process of the users, being necessary to complement these
404 dimensions with others that may influence each strategy (e.g. the use-context of a specific system) and
405 3) the difficulty on validating the measurement and categorisation of the dimensions makes necessary
406 to apply specific rules and measures to each context and/or strategy.

407 6. Conclusions and future work

408 This piece of research proposes a holistic meta-model of the user based on behavioural dimensions
409 applied to foster the motivation about sustainable lifestyle. It aims at facing the heterogeneity of the
410 individuals through a dynamic categorisation to offer a flexible framework to be applied in the ideation
411 and development of Smart Environments.

412 Although further research is needed to extract validated findings of the model and its performance,
413 this work sets a starting point to develop a person-centred approach and to target users' needs
414 addressing diversity and complexity of people when facing pro-environmental awareness.

415 This proposal sets research lines that are included as a future work that should be developed to
416 extract more knowledge and solid findings on this early work. 1) an in-depth analysis and study of the
417 meta-model in order to validate it and to better define and measure the categories of each dimension;
418 2) testing of the model with different groups and individuals (i.e. specific target users, researchers,
419 practitioners...) to include valuable insights from different points of view and to validate the proposed
420 framework; 3) Complement the model with other specific and context-related dimensions that may
421 influence users' behaviour; and 4) explore the application of the model with different methods in
422 different phases to better understand its possibilities.

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